

Reaching Out to Openness

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.... the horizontally outstretched Pathaka hands come forward.....
closer towards the chest forming Shikara seated on Pathaka which then
encircles the Shikara...igniting....
to produce sparks of Tripathaka which rise
into a jwala above the head.....opening into an Alapadma...
....a padma with its petals reaching far and wide,

Alapadma with fingers held so taut that they seem to extend beyond the
proscenium towards the audience.

This was the feeling that I had the first time
I watched Padmini Chettur positioned in an
extended split with her hastas which appeared
to come alive encircling her and the viewer at
the same moment. That a dancer could charge
the space even with simple but strongly held
hand gestures and immaculately worked out
movements in *ati-vilambit kala* was being felt
tremendously.

Chandralekha's *Sharira* from which the
above segment is described, celebrates the
living body in which sexuality, sensuality and
spirituality co-exist- acknowledging no limits,
borders, boundaries. In 1984 East-West Dance
encounter at NCPA, Mumbai where she
presented *Thillana* from *Devadasi* with a
group of Kalakshetra trained dancers, she was
hailed as an iconoclast trying to break away

from tradition - a 'Classical' tradition. Her successive choreographies only seemed to further increase her alienation by the purists of 'Classical' tradition. What was overlooked here was the fact that Bharatanatyam which is said to be 'classical' dance has a history of only 200 years and was 'revived' only a few decades earlier. Chandralekha's *Thillana* presented at the encounter began the process of breaking the canons of 'classicism'. Canons in which the dancer who was *Prima donna* 'svelte and graceful with quivering lips, flashy eyelashes and a simpering smile' forever waiting for union with her beloved became a very contemporary woman who tries to come to terms with the ironies of reality and meets them head-on.

This woman has an enviable body posture. She dances with an honesty and confidence with her head held high, straight spine, reticent smile and a piercing glance with forceful adavus reinforcing her irrefutable identity and presence in an otherwise vulnerable, male dominated world. She charges the space around her and makes it pulsate not with her smile but with a resonating energy.

She reminds us of Subramanya Bharati's famous verse in tamil,

"Nimirnda nannadai, nerkkonda paarvayum,
nilatthil yaarkkum anjaada theermayum,.."

(Trnsl: "With an erect stride, unswerving gaze,
Resolve to fear no one on this land,...")

Chandralekha's works from *Devadasi* (1961) and *Navagraha* (1972) to *Sharira* (2001) are based on Indian traditional concepts which are made relevant to our present times. "Where does the body begin... and where does it end?" remained a perennial question for her. This quest continued both in her art and life. The importances of esoteric Indian concepts like mandala, yantra, navagraha, kaal, Ardhanarishwara, etc. were explored with a contemporary mind and contextualized with a modern sensibility.

From creative imagery visualized through the playful riddles of Bhaskaracharya's *Lilavati* (1989), commonness of yoga and Dance in *Prana* (1990), accentuated power of women in *Sri* (1991), Body- Abstract- in *Yantra* (1994), time and timelessness in *Mahakaal* (1995), Hidden Femininity explored in *Raga* (1998), Self and Renewal in *Sloka* (1999), and Body ascending in *Sharira* (2001), Chandra's choreographies flow from one into the other, the recurrent motifs reminding us of her concept of cyclic notions of time known to us as the *Kaalasarpa* (Primordial Serpent).

Her works reflect her search for a unifying force in our lives, to replenish and present the body as an unending resource for energizing the micro and macrocosmic universe. This is a force that enables to sustain the energy and vitality of Human Body, unleash its ultimate potential and adapt to changing times. Chandra does not leave behind institutions, Shishyas, a hallowed legacy or a repertoire to be done over and over again.

She leaves behind questions for us to raise.....
Questions.....to search for an Openness.

